

The Influence of Existentialism on Literature and Journalism in Southern Vietnam from 1954 to 1975

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ABSTRACT: Existentialism is a philosophical and literary movement that originated in Europe in the early 20th century, gaining significant momentum after World War II. This movement emphasizes human existence, individual freedom, and the responsibility of each person in creating meaning in their lives. This article concludes that existentialism had a considerable influence on the literature and journalism of Southern Vietnam during the period from 1954 to 1975. The presence and impact of existentialism can be observed through intellectuals and researchers, enriching the literature, philosophy, and journalism of Vietnam during this period.

Keywords: influence, existentialism, Southern Vietnam, literature, Vietnam

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1. Introduction

The period from 1954 to 1975 was a tumultuous era in Vietnamese history. Following the Geneva Accords of 1954, Vietnam was divided into two regions, with the North adopting socialism and the South embracing a republican regime. The outbreak of the Vietnam War led to profound social and political changes, affecting all aspects of life, including literature and philosophy. One of the Western philosophical theories introduced to Vietnam and widely influential during the years 1954-1975 was existentialism. Southern Vietnam, with its diverse thoughts and Western cultural influences, provided fertile ground for existentialism to develop and spread. Renowned existential philosophers such as Jean-Paul Sartre, Albert Camus, Simone de Beauvoir, Martin Heidegger, and Soren Kierkegaard significantly influenced many intellectuals, writers, journalists, and students in the South. The influence of existentialism manifested in various aspects from theoretical discussions to creative works, impacting both professionals and the general readership. In literature and journalism, many Southern writers and journalists were profoundly affected by existentialism. Notable literary and journalistic works from this period bore the distinct imprint of existential thought, addressing themes like loneliness, the absurdity of life, and the struggle to find personal meaning in a chaotic world. Numerous magazines and academic forums became vibrant spaces for exchanging and discussing issues related to existentialism. Existential philosophy gradually became an attractive and compelling intellectual trend among many intellectuals and young people. Initially, existentialism had a modest presence in schools under the Ngô Đình Diệm government, but from 1961 onwards, with the fall of the Ngô Đình Diệm regime, existentialism was widely and systematically introduced in the press. Numerous works and studies on existentialism were published, invigorating cultural life.

Southern researchers endeavored to introduce existentialism from general overviews to detailed analyses, examining prominent philosophers and comparing existential philosophy with other philosophical thoughts, particularly Buddhist philosophy. Existentialism created a new wave of thought, promoting innovation in literature, philosophy, and journalism in Southern Vietnam during this period, thereby enriching the cultural and intellectual landscape of Vietnam during a time of great upheaval.

2. Methodology

The article employs several fundamental research methods in the fields of social sciences and humanities, including the historical method, text analysis method, comparative method, and statistical method.

Historical Method: This method will be used to analyze the historical context of Vietnam during the period from 1954 to 1975. By examining political, social, and cultural events, the study will identify factors that influenced the introduction and development of existentialism in Southern Vietnam. Historical documents, journalism, legal texts, and other primary sources will be the main materials for this section.

Text Analysis Method: This method will be employed to study literary works, journalism, and philosophical essays on existentialism. The works of Southern writers, journalists, and philosophers will be analyzed to understand how existentialism was expressed and applied in these works. Themes such as loneliness, the absurdity of life, and the struggle to find personal meaning will receive special attention.

Comparative Method: This method will be used to compare existential philosophy with other philosophical thoughts, such as Buddhism. The study will examine the similarities and differences between these perspectives, thereby clarifying the influence of existentialism on Southern Vietnam's philosophy and culture.

Statistical Method: This method will be used to analyze data related to the prevalence of existentialism during the period from 1954 to 1975. Data such as the number of published works, the frequency of existential themes in journalism, and the number of events and seminars on existentialism will be collected and analyzed.

Additionally, an interdisciplinary approach will be used to combine research methods from various fields such as history, literature, philosophy, and sociology. This combination will help the research provide a comprehensive and in-depth view of the influence of existentialism in Southern Vietnam during this period.

3. Results

Literature and Journalism in Southern Vietnam from 1954 to 1975

Peace was restored in Vietnam following the signing of the Geneva Accords on July 21, 1954. According to the agreement, the southern resistance forces regrouped to the North, while the French army and most of those working for the French migrated to the South. The French colonists and the Republic of Vietnam coerced nearly a million people

from the North to move to the South. Despite increasing repression by the Ngô Đình Diệm government, public struggles continued, and patriotic literature and journalism in the South supported these efforts. During this period, while Personalism was met with indifference, existentialism increasingly attracted intellectuals. Many graduate students and researchers chose existentialism as their research topic. Cultural and social organizations such as the French Cultural Institute, the Literary Friends Association, and the Asian Cultural Foundation organized lectures on existentialism. Existential philosophy gradually became an appealing intellectual trend among many intellectuals and youth, despite its modest presence in schools. The dominant ideology in urban Southern Vietnam at the time was the Personalism of Ngô Đình Diệm. However, there were several writings on existentialism in books and journals, such as "Literature and Metaphysics" by Nguyễn Văn Trung (1957), "General Observations on Existential Philosophy" by Nguyễn Sa (1957), "Buddhism and J.P. Sartre's Existentialism" (Quang Minh, 1958), and "Concepts of Existentialism" by Quang Minh (1959). These writings provided readers with the basic issues of existential philosophy, from general overviews to specific authors, helping them quickly become familiar with this philosophy. Moreover, the authors of these writings often endorsed existential philosophy, seeing it as a new philosophy worth promoting because it defended humanity, sympathized with suffering, and encouraged people to fulfill their noble missions. In the article "The Literary Standpoint of Albert Camus," Cô Liêu pointed out, "Camus uses literature to express philosophical thoughts. The artist must reject the absurdity of life and elevate life to a higher level. These principles inspire many ideas about literary creation, about the constructive element in literature, the witness of the era, and great works" (Cô Liêu, 1960). Cô Liêu delved deeply into existential philosophy and praised it as "a method of awakening conscience to establish new values for life" (Cô Liêu, 1960). To meet readers' passion for existentialism, journals at the time, such as *Đại Học*, *Sáng Tạo*, *Văn*, and *Bách Khoa*, published many articles and special issues on this philosophical and literary trend and authors like Jean-Paul Sartre and Albert Camus. Supporting this research was an increasing effort in translation, bringing the works of existential authors to a wider audience. Theoretical works included those of F. Nietzsche, K. Jaspers, M. Heidegger, and J.-P. Sartre. Creative works included novels and literary scripts by A. Camus, J.-P. Sartre, S. de Beauvoir, and F. Sagan. From October 1961 to September 1962, in the *Bách Khoa* journal, under the pen name Trần Hương Tử, Trần Thái Đĩnh wrote a series of articles introducing existentialism, which were later compiled into the monograph "Existential Philosophy" (Trần, T. Đ, 1968). With clear writing and flexible explanations from a knowledgeable writer, Trần Thái Đĩnh's book transcended academic boundaries, reaching a broad readership and having a significant impact at the time. After presenting an overview of existentialism, its themes, and its main branches, the author deeply analyzed the views of Kierkegaard, Nietzsche, Husserl, Jaspers, Marcel, Sartre, and Heidegger. Trần Thái Đĩnh expressed sympathy for the views of Kierkegaard, Jaspers, and Marcel—who were theistic existentialists—and did not hide his dislike for Nietzsche and Sartre—who were atheistic existentialists. He criticized Sartre as being "excessive in his words and lacking a constructive spirit" (Trần, T. Đ, 1968, p. 380) and considered Sartre's philosophy as individualistic, selfish, bourgeois, and arrogant. Trần Thái Đĩnh even described Sartre as "cruel, malicious, and shortsighted" in his view of human relations. He agreed with the concept of the Other, valuing both "the I" and "the we" as G. Marcel did, while Sartre and

Camus affirmed loneliness and misunderstanding as a fate humans must endure. According to Trần Thái Đĩnh, Sartre's philosophy was "suffocating" because it "did not allow humans to reach up to God," something Jaspers and Marcel always mentioned through the concepts of "transcendence" and "comprehensive being." In this respect, Sartre followed Nietzsche's path: "God is dead!" When God is dead, humans have nothing to cling to and are allowed to do anything. Trần Thái Đĩnh believed Sartre's philosophy was one-sided because it cut off human connections both horizontally and vertically: horizontally, it did not extend to others; vertically, it did not elevate towards God. In introducing existentialism, Trần Thái Đĩnh was influenced by Mounier's evaluation of Sartre. Trần Thái Đĩnh saw Mounier's Personalism as "an attempt to synthesize the advantages of both existentialism and Marxism while striving to avoid the extremes of these two theories" (Trần, T. Đ, 1968, p. 375). The critique of Sartre's atheism was not without echoes of the anti-atheism policy of the Republic of Vietnam regime at the time. This explains why Trần Thái Đĩnh initially paid little attention to Heidegger but, after reading "Letter on Humanism," changed his attitude and discovered that Heidegger's philosophy was a "gateway" to faith or at least not contrary to Christian faith. As a devout cleric and teacher, Trần Thái Đĩnh found it difficult to share the bleak worldview and rebellious attitude of Sartre, Simone de Beauvoir, and F. Sagan. In the opening lines of "Existential Philosophy," Trần Thái Đĩnh wrote: "Existentialism contains many good seeds mixed with many bad seeds: the beautiful aspects attract young people, but because they are not discerning enough to distinguish, they also swallow the poison mixed within" (Trần, T. Đ, 1968, p. 10). Concluding the chapter "Sartre—Absurd Existentialism," Trần Thái Đĩnh commented: "Sartre lacks love, but he lives in luxury, with a substantial fortune. Sartre's spiritual child, Sagan, also belongs to the bourgeoisie, with plenty of money, enjoying all that human desires can crave. Even today, if bourgeois living ends, so will Sartre's existential poison. The industrious Vietnamese people demand a philosophy more suitable for their way of life" (Trần, T. Đ, 1968, p. 349). While Trần Thái Đĩnh did not pay enough attention to Heidegger's role in the development of existential thought, Lê Tôn Nghiêm—also a priest and professor at the University of Literature, Saigon—gave this philosopher significant attention. He wrote two substantial works to present Heidegger's philosophy: "Heidegger and the Collapse of Western Thought" (Lê, T. N, 1970) and "What is the Origin of Thought or the Philosophical Path from Kant to Heidegger" (Lê, T. N, 1970). In the first book, the author introduced Heidegger as a solution to the problems and dead-ends of modern Western philosophy. In the second book, in a broader context following the development of thought from the Modern period, Lê Tôn Nghiêm showed Heidegger's contributions in answering Kant's questions in the "Critique of Pure Reason" about human issues (What can I know? What should I do? What can I hope for?), progressing to solve the fundamental question that underpins answering the previous questions: "What is the essence of human existence," aiming to lay the foundation for the science of anthropology. Unlike Trần Thái Đĩnh, who had a clear, accessible writing style, Lê Tôn Nghiêm often expressed deep philosophical issues in a heavy manner. He typically followed the internal logic of philosophical thought with little relation to the surrounding cultural life context. Delving into specialized issues and capturing the original sources of philosophy was also the direction of the journal "Tư Tưởng" (Thought) — the theoretical body of Vạn Hạnh University — when it organized a special issue on Husserl's phenomenology (new series, issue 1, June 1, 1969) with articles by Phạm Công Thiện

(Phenomenology and Husserl's Phenomenology), Ngô Trọng Anh (The Problem of Reality in Husserl's Phenomenology), and Lê Tôn Nghiêm (The Transcendental Environment in Husserl's Phenomenology of Life).

The period from 1961 to 1975 witnessed a vigorous development of existentialism in print media, exerting profound influence on society. The collapse of the Ngô Đình Diệm regime and its ideology, coupled with the stifling conditions and impasse in people's lives amidst the intensity of war, provided fertile ground for existentialism to take deeper root and flourish. As existentialism humanism lost its firm footing in the social and spiritual life, the Saigon government aimed to harness existentialism as a new ideological tool to construct a modern colonial cultural foundation. From 1961 onward, existential philosophy was widely introduced and systematically disseminated in the press. Numerous works and studies on existentialism were published, enriching cultural life. From January 1961 to November 1962, the journal *Bách Khoa* featured a series introducing existentialism by author Trần Hương Tử (pen name of Trần Thái Đĩnh). With concise style and simple presentation, these articles quickly resonated with a wide readership. Trần Hương Tử sequentially introduced from an overview of existentialism to prominent existentialists. For each philosopher, the author highlighted key issues: Kierkegaard - the pioneer of honest existentialism; Nietzsche - the atheist existentialist; Jaspers - existentialism and transcendence. The author emphasized the significant differences between theistic and atheistic existentialism and among existentialist philosophers. These articles demonstrated meticulous and serious research. In 1967, this series was compiled into "Existential Philosophy." Subsequently, many articles and works on existential philosophy continued to be introduced and published. Most prominent existentialist philosophers such as Kierkegaard, Heidegger, Nietzsche, and Sartre were sequentially introduced. Existential philosophy not only introduced the main content or general spirit of each philosopher but also was deeply studied and compared through various lenses, juxtaposed with other philosophical thoughts to find uniqueness or similarities. Particularly, existential philosophy was often viewed in comparison with Buddhist thought. Before existential philosophy deeply embedded itself in urban Southern society, Buddhism had a widespread influence there. Buddhist thought and existentialist thought shared many similarities, such as views on the suffering of life and the humble, solitary nature of human existence. Articles comparing existentialism with Buddhism include: "Entering Buddhism through the avenue of J.P. Sartre" by Thích Đức Nhuận (Thích, Đ. N, 1964); "Nietzsche and Mật Tông" by Ngô Trọng Anh (Ngô, T. A, 1970); "Buddha and Nietzsche" by Chơn Hạnh (Chơn Hạnh, 1970); and "Contemplation on death in the thoughts of Heidegger and Buddhism" by Chơn Hạnh (Chơn Hạnh, 1971). The issues of existential philosophy were thoroughly explored and scrutinized from one philosopher to another, such as "Time through Kant, Hegel, and Husserl" by Ngô Trọng Anh (Ngô, T. A, 1968); "From phenomenology of Husserl to phenomenology of Heidegger" by Trần Công Tiến (Trần, C. T, 1971), etc. If in previous periods, existential philosophy was only introduced through newspaper articles, in this period, there were many extensive studies on it, exemplified by Lê Tôn Nghiêm with works like "Heidegger before the collapse of Western thought" (Lê, T. N, 1970); "What is the origin of thought or the philosophical path from Kant to Heidegger" (Lê, T. N, 1970); "Issues of modern philosophy" (Lê, T. N, 1971); Lê Thành Trị with the study "Phenomenological discourse on existentialism" (Lê, T. T, 1969); "General philosophy" by Nguyễn Văn Trung (Nguyễn, V. T, 1967); Nghiêm Xuân Hồng with "Atoms,

existentialism, and void" (Nghiêm, X. H, 1969), Bùi Giáng with "Modern thought" (Bùi Giáng, 1974), etc. Researchers like Tam Ích, Vũ Đình Lưu, Thế Phong, Nguyễn Trọng Văn, Đặng Phùng Quân, Huỳnh Phan Anh, Trần Xuân Kiêm, Trần Công Tiến, Nguyễn Quốc Trụ, also contributed many works and articles on existential philosophy, making it the most influential intellectual trend during this period. The attitudes of researchers towards existentialism varied: conservative intellectuals often viewed it as a foreign, chaotic, and disruptive phenomenon, while many young intellectuals, though not fully understanding existentialism, welcomed it eagerly as a vague yet hopeful message. Trần Thái Đĩnh's perspective, as stated in the "Preface" of "Existential Philosophy" published in 1967, highlighted these attitudes: "Existential philosophy can also be dangerous and ugly. But where exactly is the danger and ugliness? For how long have we failed to speak honestly and accurately, while young people still do not heed us, and the danger persists. Existential theory contains many good elements mixed with bad seeds: precisely because those attractive aspects have seduced young people, but because they are not discerning enough, they swallow the poisonous mixtures within." (Trần, T. Đ, 1968, pp. 15-16). Therefore, Trần Thái Đĩnh advocates for "clear differentiation" in all praise and criticism, so that existential philosophy is understood and evaluated correctly. In the "Preface" of "Phenomenology of Existence", author Lê Thành Trĩ also expresses a similar opinion: "Not only in Vietnam but almost everywhere in the world, existentialism is often understood as a bizarre, passionate, reckless, defiant lifestyle, regardless of public opinion and morality. Under these guises, existentialism is scrutinized by Ethics and National Tradition with skeptical, disdainful eyes. But if existentialism is only that, then the public would have been somewhat unjust to the figures who directly or indirectly gave birth to the existential movement, and we would not have been encouraged to make efforts to present this research compendium." He evaluates existential philosophy as "the philosophy of wayward individuals in the twentieth century" (Lê, T. T, 1969, p. 6) and expresses, "In writing this book, we have no hope other than to help some people understand the true meaning of existential philosophy" (Lê, T. T, 1969, p. 6). In his work "Modern Issues in Philosophy" (Lê, T. N, 1971), Lê Tôn Nghiêm dedicates a chapter to "The Existential Movement in Sociology", where he links existentialism with Max Weber's sociological theory. Lê Tôn Nghiêm passionately praises the founders of existential philosophy: "Kierkegaard and Nietzsche were horrified to see clearly that humanity was plunging into a deep abyss, and they tried to awaken the sleeping world. They are essential figures for us to achieve intense experiences. At present, they have not yet achieved their goal of awakening humanity" (Lê, T. N, 1971, p. 158). Later, the author analyzes the four currents of existentialism that he identifies as "the philosophy of essence" by Heidegger, "the philosophy of emotional activity" by Scheler, "phenomenological ontology" by Sartre, and "phenomenological dualism" by Merleau-Ponty. Compared to Trần Thái Đĩnh, Lê Tôn Nghiêm is less biased against atheistic existentialists and also discusses existentialism in relation to Marxism in a relaxed manner. For example, he writes: "In general, Merleau-Ponty viewed Marxist theory as a very grand theoretical method, but it had to be used to suit the exploration and had to be reviewed in the light of different historical conditions when applied there" (Lê, T. N, 1971, p. 209). Similarly, taught at the Western Philosophy Department of Saigon University, like Trần Thái Đĩnh, Lê Tôn Nghiêm, and as the dean of the department in the final years of the war, Lê Thành Trĩ has compiled a monograph "On the Phenomenon of Phenomenon" (Lê, T. T, 1969). This title imitates two works: Hegel's Phenomenon of

Spirit and Merleau-Ponty's Phenomenon of Perception. Giving readers the impression that the author applied the phenomenon to describe human existentialism, but in reality, this is a summary of the development of existential philosophy, from its general significance to its expression in representative philosophers: Kierkegaard, Nietzsche, Jaspers, Sartre, and Heidegger.

When discussing existentialism in South Vietnam during the historical period of 1954-1975, Nguyen Van Trung deserves significant recognition. Not only was he a prominent philosophy professor who extensively wrote about this trend, but his works also resonated deeply during those years. Nguyen Van Trung can be considered the primary bridge introducing existentialism into Southern Vietnamese society, influencing intellectuals, artists, and students alike. Collaborating with Tran Thai Dinh, Le Ton Nghiem, and Le Thanh Tri at the Western Philosophy Department of the Saigon Faculty of Arts, where he served as Head of Department and Dean, Nguyen Van Trung did not specialize exclusively in existentialism like his aforementioned colleagues. However, existentialist ideas, particularly those of J.-P. Sartre, profoundly permeated his philosophical and literary research, evident in both his political stance and social activities. Despite sharing Christianity with Tran Thai Dinh, Nguyen Van Trung adopted a markedly different stance on existentialism. Whereas his predecessors leaned towards theistic existentialism, he inclined towards atheistic existentialism. While they primarily viewed existentialism as a subject of study, he predominantly regarded it as a philosophy of life, a way of being and living. Returning to Vietnam after studying in Europe, Nguyen Van Trung initially introduced and applied existentialism in analyzing and evaluating various literary phenomena in his early articles in *Dai Hoc* magazine. Subsequently, through works like "General Philosophy," "Introduction to Philosophy," "Overview of Literature," and "Constructing Literary Works," he repeatedly introduced Sartrean ideas. Readers in South Vietnam became acquainted with concepts like "commitment," "choice," and "bad faith," partly due to Nguyen Van Trung's introductory philosophy books. In literary theory, he certainly referenced J.-P. Sartre's "What is Literature?" when writing "Overview of Literature" (Volume I: General Issues), which posed and addressed questions such as what to write, why write, and for whom to write. Naturally, in theoretical terms, Nguyen Van Trung not only applied Sartre's ideas but also introduced literary thoughts from Heidegger, Barthes, and others. In practical terms, he closely observed and shed light on Vietnamese literary phenomena. Similarly, in volumes II (Language of Literature and Drama) and III (Literary Research and Criticism), Nguyen Van Trung introduces the ideas of Sartre alongside those of P. Valéry, A. Robbe-Grillet, Ch. Mauron, G. Bachelard, L. Goldmann, and others, aimed at applying them to resolve issues arising from literary history. It can be said that, up to that point, in Vietnam, these books constituted a systematically updated theoretical framework of modern ideas. For Nguyen Van Trung, Sartre was not only a cultural phenomenon but also a spiritual anchor, a source of shared understanding and solutions to human issues in specific life contexts. In his essay "Sartre in My Life," he wrote: "Sartre yearned to find a philosophy that would bring true meaning to life. In other words, Sartre viewed philosophy as something essential, necessary, intimately linked to life; not merely a theoretical or abstract combat" (Nguyen, V. T., 1968, p. 32). He found in Sartre a suitable direction of thought for intellectuals committed to action: "We do not live in any other era than our own. There may be eras more peaceful, more beautiful, but they are not ours, an era of hot and cold wars between two blocs, an era

threatened frequently by atomic bombs, an era of imperialism, colonial aggression,... We have no choice over our circumstances, our era, but we can only choose within our circumstances, our era" (Nguyen, V. T., 1968, p. 19). The reception of existentialism by Nguyen Van Trung and some intellectuals inclined in South Vietnam also corresponds to two stages of development in Sartre's thought. The initial stage is closely associated with Nguyen Van Trung's writings during his collaboration with *Dai Hoc* magazine and his editorial works before 1965, clearly reflecting the influence of existentialist reflections in the Real and the Void. The subsequent stage is linked to activities in newspapers like *Hanh Trinh*, *Dat Nuoc*, deeply influenced by the *Critique of Dialectical Reason* and magazines such as *Les Temps modernes*, *J'accuse*. This change in Nguyen Van Trung's attitude towards Sartre was not a complete break or rupture in perception but a dynamic process influenced by circumstances, akin to Sartre's attitude towards Flaubert. Not coincidentally, in the final issue of *Trinh Bay* magazine, after numerous seizures and before its suspension due to Decree 007 of the Nguyen Van Thieu regime, editor-in-chief The Nguyen reprinted excerpts from Sartre's "Literature of Extreme Situations," taken from *Situations II* (Do, L. V., 1972). However, amidst the peace, national, and democratic movements at that time, intellectuals increasingly found existentialism too confining for their thoughts on contemporary times, their country, and humanity. Nguyen Ngoc Lan and Ly Chanh Trung were preoccupied with timely political commentaries, hardly writing about existentialism. Some younger writers both admired Sartre's intellectual qualities and resisted the illusions of existentialism. Nguyen Trong Van saw existential literature as a form of intellectual posturing and cautioned against the unintended consequences of its propagation, through the imagery of "Nguyen Van Trung's wild children" (Nguyen, T. V., 1968). *Thế Nguyên* criticized "existential literature" as a form of "tail-following literature," a consequence of the "habit of pursuing sophistication" in Southern Vietnamese society (*Thế Nguyên*, 1968). Alongside this, many works by existentialist philosophers were translated and widely introduced, such as Heidegger's works: "What Is Metaphysics?" (Heidegger, M, 1974); "What Is Called Thinking?" (Heidegger, M, 1974); "Being and Time" (Heidegger, M, 1973); "On the Essence of Truth" (Heidegger, M, 1968); "Letter on Humanism" (Heidegger, M, 1974); "Albert Camus with 'Resistance and Rebellion'" (Camus, A, 1968); "The Stranger" (Camus, A, 1968); "Caligula" (Camus, A, 1967); "The Fall" (Camus, A, 1967); "The Plague" (Camus, A, 1971); "The Misunderstanding" (Camus, A, 1972); "The Myth of Sisyphus" (Camus, A, 1972); "The Mission of Modern Literature" (Camus, A, 1974); "Jean-Paul Sartre with 'Nausea'" (Sartre, J. P, 1967); "The Wall" (Sartre, J. P, 1973); "The Reprieve" (Sartre, J. P, 1966); "Dirty Hands" (Sartre, J. P, 1965); "Schopenhauer with 'The Metaphysics of Love and Death'" (Schopenhauer, A, 1971),... These works, translated and widely published, brought existentialist philosophy to urban readers in South Vietnam, facilitating the study and understanding of existentialism. Research on existentialist philosophy by foreign authors was also extensively published and introduced, such as "Existentialism of Foulque" (Thụ Nhân, 1965), "Major Trends of Modern Thought by Môroa Ăngđrê" (Tràng Thiện, 1964), "Existential Themes of Mounier" (Thụ Nhân, 1970). From 1960 onwards, existentialism was the most frequently mentioned philosophical trend, with the deepest impact on society. However, there was diversity in the reception, evaluation, and interpretation of existentialism during this period. Some supported existentialism with theism, while others adhered to atheistic existentialism. Even within atheistic existentialism,

some favored Sartre while others were enamored with Camus. Some emphasized one aspect, while others focused on another aspect of existentialism... This diversity is not surprising, as existentialism itself has "three or four existential dimensions" (Trần, T. Đ, 1968). Even Trần Thái Đĩnh, one of the first authors to dedicate significant time and effort to the study and introduction of existentialist philosophy, admitted to occasional misunderstandings in his perception of existentialist philosophers. When compiling essays on existentialism into books, he acknowledged his shortcomings in evaluating Heidegger: "Today, reviewing those essays for publication, I feel that I greatly underestimated Heidegger. Frankly, back then, I was influenced by some of my professors in Paris, especially R. Verneaux: they labeled Heidegger as inclined towards atheism and negativity. I deeply regret having allocated such limited space to Heidegger in those essays. If I could rewrite those sections, I would certainly give Heidegger the prominence he deserves" (Trần, T. Đ, 1968, pp. 12-13). This back-and-forth demonstrates that existentialist philosophy was studied with meticulous and serious effort. Existentialism had a profound influence on all aspects of social life: philosophical theory, literary creation, journalism, and human attitudes... Especially in literary creation, the influence of existentialist philosophy was more pronounced than ever before. Within this influence, both in the realm of social life and artistic literary creation, there were both positive and negative impacts. At times, the negative impacts predominated. In many works of artistic literature, the negative influence of existentialist philosophy, combined with the darker aspects of psychoanalysis, sometimes led to prejudiced views in the literary and urban journalism of South Vietnam from 1954 to 1975.

Some assessments of the influence of existentialism in the literature and journalism of South Vietnam during the period 1954-1975

Firstly, in terms of literary creation: Existentialism in South Vietnam during the period 1954-1975 was closely associated with the formation of a group of researchers, primarily within the university circle, spanning two generations: the first generation including Nguyễn Văn Trung, Trần Thái Đĩnh, Lê Tôn Nghiêm, Lê Thành Trị, Tam Ích, Nghiêm Xuân Hồng,... and the second generation including Vũ Đình Lưu, Thế Phong, Nguyễn Trọng Văn, Đặng Phùng Quân, Huỳnh Phan Anh, Trần Xuân Kiêm, Trần Công Tiến, Nguyễn Quốc Trụ, Trần Nhật Tân, Nguyễn Nhật Duật,... Perhaps no other period in Vietnam has seen existentialism studied as extensively and from as many angles as during this time. However, in terms of existential criticism, there have not been many outstanding works. The works of Lê Tuyên and Đỗ Long Vân mainly applied existential psychoanalysis to illuminate the artistic world of classical poets, rather than directly critiquing contemporary literary works. Patriotic literature and journalism fundamentally continued to be guided by the revolution through its core cadre in Saigon. The literary and journalistic activities during this period also had significant impacts on the international media, leveraging the credibility of international news agencies and foreign journalists present in Saigon in disseminating news globally. If patriotic literature and journalism did everything possible on the ideological front to contribute to the overall strength of the nation during the resistance against the US-backed Saigon regime, then conversely, the Saigon regime, with robust support from the US, also valued this weapon. Existentialism brought significant changes to literature and journalism in South Vietnam, with its artistic concept of lonely individuals in an irrational

world, using language and descriptive techniques to discuss philosophical phenomena. This influence could be spontaneous or conscious, among writers and journalists who directly read existentialist theories and engaged in literary and journalistic works in Western Europe. "Due to shared aspirations, existentialism found fertile ground in South Vietnam for a time. It was a current flowing from thought to action, from attitudes to life; where each individual became part of collective entities; spreading from intellectual circles to broader social strata; directly influencing many fields of literature, arts, music, and painting" (Cung, T. B, 2001, p. 69). "Existentialism had a profound influence on various genres of Southern Vietnamese literature, including drama, poetry, and novels. The plays of Samuel Beckett and Eugene Ionesco were widely introduced, contributing to changes in staging and the content of plays in the South during this period" (Saigon literature, 2023). "The press in the South also flourished during this period, with many magazines and weekly newspapers introducing and discussing Western philosophical trends, particularly existentialism. This richness created a vibrant environment for debates and seminars on culture and philosophy, allowing existentialism to penetrate deeply into the intellectual and artistic circles" (Nguyễn, T. V. N, 2023).

Secondly, in terms of attitude towards life: The period from 1954 to 1975 witnessed a close relationship between journalism and literature. In fact, practically every daily newspaper, weekly, semi-monthly, or monthly publication printed several short stories, novels, etc. This relationship was reinforced and bonded due to readers' demand, attracting numerous writers and poets to contribute to journalism. Writing for newspapers became a profession that significantly improved income for writers and poets, while also meeting the demand for entertainment, a spiritual "dish" indispensable in the daily lives of readers. Moreover, journalists of this era were implicitly understood as writers, "those who write for newspapers (then) were essentially doing literature rather than journalism" (Vũ Bằng, 1969, p. 14). The influence of existentialism was also complex. On one hand, it led to reactions of "rebellion," "enjoyment of life" among a restless youth unable to find direction in wartime, as pointed out by Lý Chánh Trung, Nguyễn Văn Xuân, Lữ Phương, Nguyễn Trọng Văn. On the other hand, it also prompted reflections on human fate, a sense of responsibility towards the nation's situation, and choices of attitudes and actions to engage for the common good. It can be said that existentialism addressed the concerns and desire for self-affirmation of individuals amidst the intense national conditions, demanding intellectuals not merely stand "on the sidelines of history." They lived that philosophy rather than performing translation or pure information work in the cold language of academia.

Thirdly, in terms of reception: There were significant divisions in the reception of existentialism in South Vietnam. There were at least three divisions. First, there was a divide between those who embraced existentialism with religious undertones and those who supported atheistic existentialism. Of course, this division was not absolute, as those who leaned towards Kierkegaard did not necessarily reject Nietzsche, and those who favored Marcel did not necessarily reject Sartre, and vice versa. Second, there was a split between those who favored atheistic existentialism in their attitudes towards Sartre and Camus. Those inclined towards Camus shared more philosophical and literary views with him rather than with Sartre, while the reverse was true for Sartre enthusiasts. Third, there was a division among those who admired Sartre: some sought to extend literature into irrational

and void realms, while others pushed theory into action within a concept of "unified action." Existentialism in South Vietnam was approached from various perspectives, all undoubtedly influenced by the social context and political stance of the writers, yet most showed the spirit of intellectual independence and self-respect, expressing their own thoughts without conformity, in their own voice. Existentialism was the philosophy of an era that will not repeat itself. Its reception, propagation, and application were also "historical opportunities." It arrived in the dire context of South Vietnamese society during 1954-1975, when people yearned for freedom and the right to contemplate their own freedom and human dignity. After the war, social circumstances changed, and existentialism no longer held a place in intellectual discourse.

4. Conclusions

After the Geneva Accords (1954), existentialism gradually gained introduction and development in South Vietnam. This period witnessed a strong growth of existential philosophy, particularly from the early 1960s onwards. Philosophers, writers, and journalists such as Trần Thái Đĩnh, Lê Tôn Nghiêm, Nguyễn Văn Trung, and many others actively contributed to the introduction and study of existentialism. They authored numerous works, articles, and translated works of prominent existential philosophers. Cultural organizations, magazines, and research institutes like the French Cultural Institute, the Literature Friends Society, and the Asia Cultural Foundation organized various activities to promote and discuss existential philosophy. In Southern Vietnamese society, there were diverse attitudes towards existentialism. For instance, Trần Thái Đĩnh criticized the atheistic aspects of Sartre and Camus, while Lê Tôn Nghiêm deeply studied and presented Heidegger's contributions to existential philosophy. Existentialism attracted the attention of intellectuals and youth seeking answers to profound questions about the meaning of life and human existence. During this period, articles, magazines, and books on existentialism were widely published. These works significantly contributed to the introduction and dissemination of existential philosophy to a broad audience of readers and intellectuals. Existentialism evolved from a novel trend to an integral part of Southern Vietnamese cultural and intellectual life, profoundly influencing the thoughts of many during this period. Authors and researchers contributed to clarifying and disseminating existential philosophy, demonstrating respect and high regard for the viewpoints of existential philosophers, despite divergent perspectives and evaluations of these philosophies.

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